

EarlyCause

Causative mechanisms & integrative models linking early-life-stress to psycho-cardio-metabolic multi-morbidity

Deliverable D2.3

Data Management Plan version 2

Reference	D2.3_EarlyCause_EBI_31122020
Lead Beneficiary	EMBL
Author(s)	Alisha Ahamed, Jeena Rajan, Guy Cochrane
Dissemination level	Public
Type	Report
Official Delivery Date	31/12/2020
Date of validation of the WP leader	10/12/2020
Date of validation by the Project Coordinator	11/12/2020
Project Coordinator Signature	

EarlyCause is funded by the European Union's H2020 Framework
Under Grant Agreement 848158

Version log

Issue Date	Version	Involved	Comments
09/12/2020	V1	Alisha Ahamed, Jeena Rajan, Guy Cochrane	1 st draft
09/12/2020	2	Katharina Heil, Karim Lekadir	First comments
10/12/2020	3	Alisha Ahamed, Jeena Rajan, Guy Cochrane	2 nd draft
11/12/2020	Final	Katharina Heil, Karim Lekadir	Final revision
	Final		Final, approved version

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the early life stress (ELS) and psycho-cardiometabolic multi-morbidity (PCM) related metadata standards and formats that have been or will be generated as part of the EarlyCause project. This is the second version of the data management plan which follows on from version 1 which was submitted in Month 6, as deliverable D2.1. The development of metadata standards and the use of appropriate ontologies will contribute to how data are displayed and available for search in the EarlyCause research platform and web portal. The recommended databases to be used in the project for the deposition of different types of data leading to long-term sustainability will also be discussed. This will enable data generated and submitted to be compliant with FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) principles¹. The project aims to make relevant data available for reusability by the community through public and specialised data repositories.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic most project partners have experienced a delay in generating data due to temporary lab closures. Therefore, this is an interim data management plan, and a further data management plan (v3) will be written and circulated internally in Month 18 to advise project partners on data management best practice as more data are generated.

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	2
2	Data Summary	4
3	Data types and formats	4
3.1	Behavioural parameters to sequencing reads in animal models	4
3.2	Cellular models to identify causal molecular mechanisms of ELS-induced multimorbidity	5
3.3	Recruiting human patients	6
4	ELIXIR Core and Deposition databases	6
5	Data Security	6
6	Summary	7
7	References	8

2 Data Summary

In order to create a useful data management plan, it is crucial to ensure that appropriate data formats and standards are developed and adhered to for maximum discoverability, reproducibility and interoperability of the data. The integration of harmonised data, data services, data standards, experimental protocols and best practices to support next-generation research in ELS and multi-morbidity will be the key features of the EarlyCause research-enabling platform.

At the human data workshop held on 20th May 2020, concerns were raised among project partners working with human cohort data regarding submission of data to the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA)² due to data confidentiality reasons. There have been no further discussions on the human cohort data deposition and it is not mentioned in this document. However, this will be addressed in the third version of the Data Management Plan to be written and circulated internally in Month 18.

Following on from the human data workshop, a virtual mouse/cell line workshop was conducted in October 2020 with an aim to gather requirements and an understanding of the data types and relevant standards to be captured in the EarlyCause project. This information will guide how data are organised and displayed on the EarlyCause research platform and web portal. Project partners working on animal/cell line data presented information on the datasets currently available and those that will be generated in the next few months. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, most of the lab work has been delayed for at least six months and hence, a second workshop is planned to be held in April 2021.

3 Data types and formats

Data types that will be generated during this project are summarised in the table below.

Human	Animal Model	Cell Line
DNA methylation profiles	Methylation	RNA-Seq
16S microbiome	RNA-Seq	'omics data aligning with animal models
GWAS	ATAC-Seq	Image
Phenotype	16s microbiome	Biochemical & cellular
Epidemiological	Epigenetic	Protein expression
Clinical	Metabolomic	Protein quantification
Inflammatory markers	Image	qPCR
	Biochemical assays	

Table 1: Data types in EarlyCause.

3.1 Behavioural parameters to sequencing reads in animal models

As a part of WP5, animal model work consists of prenatal model work on rats and postnatal model work on mice. The team at ETH-UZH is mainly involved in determination and quantification of pre- and postnatal stress on behavioural, cardiovascular and metabolic functions in adult mice. Experiments will be performed to produce a variety of data types as shown below.

Data type	Data format
Raw data	fastQ
DNA methylation data	SAM
RNA-seq	Salmon quantification files
Aligned reads	BAM
Samples by genes/samples	Counts table
Behaviour & cardi-metabolic measures/parameters	Excel sheets
Microbiome data	fastQ

Table 2: Data formats in mouse data.

A study³ has already been published on the involvement of circulating factors in transmission of paternal experience through the germline where the following datasets were generated: RNA-sequencing data, proteomics data and metabolomics data. An R package Mixomics⁴ is being used to integrate and analyse multi-omics data. The RNA-seq data has already been submitted to the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)⁵ under accession GSE154369. All other data is accessible in Excel format from the ETH Zurich's Research Collection⁶. However, in order to ensure the data are accessioned with permanent identifiers, therefore making them accessible and findable, we advise the proteomics data are submitted to the PRoteomics IDentifications Database (PRIDE)⁷, an ELIXIR Core Data Resource⁸ and Deposition Database⁹, and the metabolomics data and mouse behavioural data are deposited in MetaboLights¹⁰ and BioStudies¹¹, respectively, both ELIXIR Deposition Databases. The team at EBI will provide support and assistance for data submissions to the respective resources.

3.2 Cellular models to identify causal molecular mechanisms of ELS-induced multimorbidity

The EarlyCause team at KCL works on 5 different cell lines that are being used to mimic ELS in human cells. Cellular and biochemical readouts are generated with the help of different markers such as protein expression, protein quantification and gene expression. The data is currently stored in Excel files. A few cell types with some examples of their cellular and biochemical readouts are shown below.

Cell type	Cellular	Biochemical
Hippocampal precursors	DCX, Map2	BDNF, CDK2
Microglia	Iba1, CD11b	C1, C1q, C3
Cardiomyocytes	cTNI, N2B	α/β -myosin heavy chain
Hepatocytes	HepPar1, HRF-4 α	Glucose 6-phosphatase; glucokinase
Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs)	CD19, CD69, CD14	IRFs, JAK1, TYK2
Across all cell types	DAPI	MAPK, STAT and NFKB

Table 3: Hypothesis-driven Cellular and Biochemical Readouts.

Exome based sequencing and short RNA sequencing data will be generated and should be deposited in the ENA¹². The necessary advice and support will be provided for the same by EBI. Morphological analysis and image generation of cell lines will also be performed. The images will be extracted by generating approximately 15 images per well from 96 well plates. Several wells will be used for each experimental condition with the plates replicated several times. At least 2-3 immunofluorescence markers will be used for each plate. To support the integrity and reproducibility of the data, images can be deposited in the Bioimage Archive¹³, a public archive for image data. The deposited image

data can be used and analysed by the EarlyCause partners prior to publication and by the wider research community post publication and beyond the lifetime of the project. The archive is constructed in such a way that it is connected to data brokers as well as added value resources such as the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR)¹⁴ and The Image Data Resource (IDR)¹⁵.

3.3 Recruiting human patients

The team at CSIC-D has started to recruit depressive human patients from existing cohorts and volunteers and this is an ongoing process. The aim is to collect faecal samples to study the gut microbiome. The microbiome profiling will be carried out by conducting metagenomic and 16S analysis of this gut microbiota. Functional and taxonomic annotation of the metagenomic data and clustering and taxonomic identification using 16S data will be produced and then used for comparative analysis to identify ELS associated microbiome markers. Bacterial cocktails obtained from *in vitro* culture of bacterial selection will then be administered to *in vivo* animal during trials.

There are plans to submit the whole genome sequencing (WGS) and 16S data to ENA after filtering to remove human reads. Further discussions are needed to develop standards for metagenomic data, descriptors, harmonisation with human data and metadata to be used for mouse samples. All ELS exposure and mouse model stress descriptors can be submitted to BioSamples¹⁶.

4 ELIXIR Core and Deposition databases

Some of the ELIXIR Core and Deposition databases that are anticipated to be used in EarlyCause project are summarised in the table below.

Database	Core/Deposition	Data Type
European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)¹²	Core & Deposition	Molecular sequence data from animal models and cell lines
BioSamples¹⁶	Deposition	ELS exposure and mouse model stress descriptors
BioStudies¹¹	Deposition	Mouse behavioural data
MetaboLights¹⁰	Deposition	Metabolic profiling data
BioImage Archive¹³	Deposition	Image data
PRIDE⁷	Core & Deposition	Proteomics data
European Genome-phenome archive (EGA)²	Core & Deposition	Personally identifiable genetic and phenotypic data resulting from biomedical research projects.

Table 4: Databases in the EarlyCause Platform.

5 Data Security

Data and metadata storage in ENA and EGA are provided by the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI). Data is stored for recovery in case of a catastrophic event. Additionally, the following applies to human identifiable data stored at EMBL-EBI:

1. EMBL-EBI will manage private data from research subjects under the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA), which has robust procedures already in place for ensuring the highest level of data security, complying with the framework provided by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health's (GA4GH) "Security Technology Infrastructure Standards and

implementation practices for protecting the privacy and security of shared genomic and clinical data” (https://www.ga4gh.org/wp-content/uploads/2016May10_REV_SecInfrastructure.pdf) and outlined at https://ega-archive.org/files/European_Genome_phenome_Archive_Security_Overview.pdf.

2. Security policies in physical and electronic access to data and infrastructure are maintained following the policies in use at EMBL (ELIXIR).
3. In this respect, EMBL has dedicated security personnel to reinforce security conditions: Data centres are only accessible by accredited personnel from the EMBL.
4. Operations team with electronic access measures. Data transmission in and out of the infrastructure will use encrypted protocols (https, SSL) in all possible cases.
5. Network links will be kept to the minimum necessary to the requirements of the service (e.g. no outside network access is available at the HPC system where the EarlyCause data platform will be hosted).
6. All internal networks will be private, internet routing will be restricted to a reduced number of monitored servers.
7. User’s data will be kept private and encrypted, and only accessed by the operation personnel when necessary to solve service issues.
8. EMBL will implement a controlled access policy whereby the access decisions reside with a Data Access Committee (DAC). The DAC will be created by the data providers and will be composed of the individuals involved in the collection and analysis of the data cohort.
9. Each dataset will be covered by a Data Access Agreement (DAA), which defines the terms and conditions of use for the specified dataset/s.
10. EarlyCause will use software for authentication/authorisation services complying with GA4GH requirements in such areas as identity management, authorisation management, access control, privacy protection and audit logs.
11. The EarlyCause platform will be maintained in a virtualised system. A backup policy for data (including user credentials) will be designed and reinforced.
12. EMBL-EBI will perform regular risk assessment; risk mitigation; identity and authorisation management; audit logs and cryptography and communication security and data integrity.

6 Summary

Data submitted to the recommended databases in this report will ensure data and high-quality metadata which have permanent identifiers and comply with FAIR principles. This will enable data to be available and searchable on the EarlyCause platform, initially to project partners and then to the wider research community, allowing sustainability of the data beyond the life of the project.

7 References

- ¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016) doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18
- ² Lappalainen *et al.* The European Genome-phenome Archive of human data consented for biomedical research. *Nat Genet* 47, 692–695 (2015). doi.org/10.1038/ng.3312
- ³ van Steenwyk *et al.* Involvement of circulating factors in the transmission of paternal experiences through the germline. *EMBO J* (2020) 39:e104579 <https://doi.org/10.15252/embj.2020104579>
- ⁴ <http://mixomics.org/methods/>
- ⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>
- ⁶ <https://doi.org/20.500.11850/426674>
- ⁷ The PRIDE database and related tools and resources in 2019: improving support for quantification data. *Nucleic Acids Research*, Volume 47, Issue D1, 08 January 2019, Pages D442–D450. doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky1106
- ⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/core-data-resources>
- ⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>
- ¹⁰ Haug *et al.* MetaboLights: a resource evolving in response to the needs of its scientific community. *Nucleic Acids Research*, Volume 48, Issue D1, 08 January 2020, D440–D444. doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz1019
- ¹¹ Sarkans *et al.* The BioStudies database-one stop shop for all data supporting a life sciences study. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2018;46(D1):D1266-D1270. doi:10.1093/nar/gkx965
- ¹² Harrison *et al.* The European Nucleotide Archive in 2020. *Nucleic Acids Research*. doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa1028
- ¹³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/>
- ¹⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/emdb/empiar/>
- ¹⁵ <https://idr.openmicroscopy.org/>
- ¹⁶ Courtot *et al.* BioSamples database: an updated sample metadata hub. *Nucleic Acids Research*, Volume 47, Issue D1, 08 January 2019, D1172–D1178. doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky1061